

New CS Track COVID-19 study reveals the importance of building on existing experience

The CS Track team of researchers led by Dr. Anne Turbe (Ecoscope) and Dr. Yaela Golumbic have recently published a study that investigates the potential of citizen science to respond to emerging challenges. This report includes an analysis of Covid-19 citizen science projects using a two-phase research approach namely website content analysis and detailed case studies of seven citizen science initiatives.

The website review revealed that the covid-19 citizen science landscape was dominated by contributory crowd-sourcing projects, mainly related to health sciences. Most of the projects were purpose-developed by scientists to respond to the global Covid-19 crisis, and leveraged basic information technologies (internet, smartphones) to collect self-reported data on people's symptoms, behaviour or well-being from questionnaires.

The case studies revealed the importance of preparedness to respond to new challenges, building on existing experience, collaborations and modular software infrastructure. All case studies highlighted the significance of regular and honest feedback, to secure the trust and engagement of the participants.

The report shows there is considerable opportunity to improve the outcomes of citizen science in response to emerging challenges and includes recommendations derived from multiple projects analysis. The recommendations include not being afraid to plan for success, thinking big, open and collaboratively when designing a project and listening to the needs and expectations of contributors in order to sustain engagement.

Download the full document [here](#).

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